

Questions, Comments and Answers following the presentation

Polarimetric calibration and accuracy: lessons learnt from the existing instrumentation
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Mouillet:

1. *Best performance obtained for polarimetric accuracy?*
 2. *Status of the list of primary calibrators (in VIS and NIR)?*
1. Clearly there is the limitation of the S/N that can be obtained. Error bars are proportional to $1/\sqrt{S/N}$, and S/N may be limited by saturation limits. For instance broadband linear polarisation measurements with FORS cannot be more accurate than a few units in 10^4 unless we spend the entire observing night in reading and reading out the CCD to accumulate signal from a very limited area of the CCD. Then there is a contribution from instrumental polarisation that in imaging mode is of the order of a few units in 10^{-4} . So I think that in imaging mode, I have reached an accuracy of the order of 3×10^{-4} for object with very low polarisation. In spectropolarimetric mode instrumental polarisation may be up to 10^{-3} . This can be calibrated, but you are never sure how stable the calibration is. Finally, there is a relative uncertainty in the measurement of linear polarisation which is probably of the order of 0.3% the signal or polarisation. E.g. if you measure a fraction of linear polarisation = 1%, this could be 1.03% or 0.97%. In addition, one has to consider that in spectropolarimetric mode, tiny instrument flexures may produce spurious spikes in the Stokes profiles of spectral lines.
2. There are two articles specifically dedicated to the stars used by FORS in polarimetric mode (Fossati et al. 2007 and Cikota et al. 2017). The list of stars that can be used with large telescopes is small, but remember that in general standard stars for linear polarisation are used just to make sure that the polarimetric optics are correctly aligned, and except for special cases you do not need to observe close to your target etc. Polarimetry in the IR is less common than optical polarimetry, and this is reflected in a substantially less extended catalogue of well-established standard stars.

Smette: What would be needed to expand catalogues of polarimetric standard stars (IR, optical)?

A regular monitoring of a number of highly polarised standard stars as to make sure that stars are not variable.

Girard: Do you have a full Mueller matrix for the system telescope+instrument UT1+FOR2?

No.

Lupton: Have you considered CMOS? The detectors are much better than they used to be. You can remove the cosmic rays with non-destructive reads and the readout is fast.

I am an user and I do not participate to the design of new instruments or to the upgrade of older ones. This suggestion should be forwarded to the FORS Instrument Team.